

EU-HIP – DELIVERABLE

EU interoperability with HERA's IT platform

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¹ R = Report, P = Prototype, D = Demonstrator, O = Other

² PU = Public

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WP3 – Evaluation

D3.1 Evaluation Plan

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
D	Deliverable
EU-HIP	EU interoperability with HERA's IT platform
HERA	European Health Emergency preparedness and Response Authority
IT	Information technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
MS	Milestone
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic, and Timely
SB	Steering Board
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

For intelligence gathering and threat assessment, HERA needs support from the Member States and associated countries. In this regard, a comprehensive state-of-the-art IT system generating actionable insights for decision-making is crucial. The upcoming HERA IT platform for intelligence gathering will only be operational if Member States have strong national IT systems that are interoperable with HERA's IT system and other relevant systems.

EU-HIP supports participating countries to enhance and improve national IT systems in an efficient and coordinated manner, with the objective of obtaining the needed interoperability with HERA's IT platform. This will entail developing new IT systems and strengthening, as well as aligning existing IT systems for the assessment of health threats and for intelligence gathering in the area of medical countermeasures at national level. Moreover, there is focus on promoting data comparability, and streamlining reporting to different systems. EU-HIP will facilitate integration of national IT systems with the HERA IT platform currently under development, and complement existing systems for early warning and response, epidemic intelligence, public health surveillance and medical countermeasures.

WP3 – Evaluation is responsible for the internal evaluation of EU-HIP in order to assess if the project is being implemented as planned and reaches the predicted objectives. The first step to achieve this goal is the creation of an evaluation plan for EU-HIP.

The EU-HIP Evaluation Plan follows the project intervention logic and describes the structure of the project's internal evaluation: i) evaluation objectives, ii) roles and responsibilities, iii) methods and tools for data collection, iv) activities and v) timeline. The evaluation plan follows a SMART approach in order to ensure that the evaluation is focused, realistic and effective to inform the project overall status. The focus of the project's internal evaluation is to measure the effectiveness of the action in meeting the specific objectives and monitoring performance throughout the project's timeline. As such, the evaluation plan focuses on the project specific objectives and their encompassing KPI's. The evaluation will also use specific indicators for all WPs that will allow a timeliness and quality assessment of deliverables, an overarching requisite for effectiveness. The results of EU-HIP evaluation will be analysed in one Evaluation Report. Evaluation activities will be carried out in four main reporting periods (M5-6, M11-12, M22-23 and M27-28), defined in accordance with evaluation reports timeline.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

The overall concept is that EU-HIP brings a high number of countries together to work towards a common aim to strengthen IT systems to ensure interoperability with HERA's IT platform. Key aspects are the inherent links to national structures and close collaboration with HERA and other Member States not part of EU-HIP.

The project will substantially strengthen national IT systems and launch an important co-creation and collaboration with HERA for intelligence gathering and medical countermeasures. As a consortium, EU-HIP will maximise the use of knowledge, expertise, experiences and resources, and enable exchange of knowledge and experiences. The wide geographical representation is a major strength in the approach of having one large, comprehensive consortium.

The work begins with focus on Specific Objective 1 “Obtain an overview of current key aspects of national IT systems and assess the compatibility with HERA's IT platform” in relation to the main features of HERA's IT platform, and a description of the national authorities' needs concerning IT software, infrastructure, and processes to ensure operational and technical interoperability with HERA's IT platform for intelligence gathering. The outcome serves as the baseline against which the progress towards addressing the needs and progressing towards the common aim of strengthening IT systems to ensure interoperability with HERA's IT platform can be measured.

The identified needs of EU-HIP are addressed by specific activities in WP5, while the overarching WPs 1–4 (Table 1) ensure coordination and efficient dissemination, evaluation and actions to address any observations, and sustainability.

TABLE 1– OVERVIEW OF EU-HIP WORK PACKAGES (WP)

#WP	WP Title	WP Description
WP1	Project management and coordination	WP1 ensures the coordination and management of the project and its implementation as planned.
WP2	Communication and Dissemination	WP2 is responsible for the communication and efficient dissemination of the results and deliverables of the project to the target groups and citizens.
WP3	Evaluation	WP3 verifies that the project is being implemented as planned and reaches the objectives.
WP4	Sustainability	WP4 focuses on the sustainability opportunities and challenges and collaborates closely with WP1 (structures and processes in the consortium and with stakeholders) and with WP5 (country-specific aspects).
WP5	Focus on specific technical needs	WP5 focuses on specific technical needs identified at the country-level to work towards strengthening and harmonization to suit with HERA IT system.

1.2. Purpose and scope of the evaluation plan

WP3 – Evaluation is responsible for the project's internal evaluation and aims to measure the effectiveness of the action in meeting the specific objectives. WP3 will monitor the performance throughout the project's timeline, thus allowing to address any relevant observations in a timely and efficient manner. This work will be conducted in close cooperation with all WPs.

The first step to achieve this goal is the creation of the evaluation plan for EU-HIP that is described in this Deliverable 3.1 – Evaluation Plan. The evaluation plan builds on the structure of the action's plan, taking into consideration the project specific objectives and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), as well as WPs' specific objectives and indicators. The evaluation plan follows a SMART approach in order to ensure that the evaluation is focused, realistic and effective to inform the project overall status.

The results of EU-HIP evaluation will be materialised in two Evaluation Reports: the interim evaluation report (Milestone 6) and the final evaluation report (Deliverable 3.2). The evaluation report will focus mainly on monitoring KPI's and indicators for all WPs as well as any deviations from the project's planned timeline.

2. Objectives and principles

The overall goal of WP3 – Evaluation is to verify that the project reaches its foreseen objectives and to ensure sustainability. Therefore, a continuous internal project evaluation will be performed in order to determine and monitor the timely delivery of documents and milestone achievement, and proper performance of the different Work Packages.

WP3 will perform its activities in three phases, as presented below:

- I. **Phase 1** 'Project Evaluation Plan': the first deliverable is D3.1 – Evaluation plan (i.e., this document). The main activity within this phase is the development of the evaluation framework with the determination of Key Performance Indicators on WP level.
- II. **Phase 2** 'Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation': ongoing evaluation in accordance with the strategy outlined in phase 1. All EU-HIP participants will have access to the results, which will be presented at relevant project meetings. During the continuous monitoring, the need to adjust the evaluation plan may be identified, especially considering the interdependency with HERA developments.
- III. **Phase 3** 'Final evaluation': the project evaluation report (D3.2) will be built on the assessment of the 30 months of the project.

The main objective of the evaluation plan is to create a strategy that describes the internal evaluation for the project, which will be conducted in close cooperation with the coordination and all WPs and task leaders. This document will present the:

1. the methodology used as the basis for the evaluation plan,
2. the defined evaluation criteria,
3. the responsibility within the project,
4. the method for data collection,
5. the source of verification,
6. the time of verification and
7. the internal monitoring strategy for WP3.

3. Evaluation Plan

WP3 will undertake an evaluation using a mixed-methods approach that combines both quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques. The overall methodology has been divided in the following phases:

- Definition of the evaluation framework
- Creation of the evaluation criteria and time of verification
- Presentation and validation of the evaluation criteria by the coordination and WP / task leaders
- Creation of the evaluation tools

3.1. Evaluation framework

The evaluation framework has 8 main steps that were created to ensure the sustainability of WP3 evaluation plan and the assessment of the achievements of EU-HIP (Figure 1).

FIGURE 1 – WP3 EVALUATION FRAMEWORK.

Firstly, WP3 helped to define and map the relationships between the planned WP objectives and general EU-HIP's objectives / KPIs. This step was essential to ensure that the specific

objectives of each WP were aligned with the main goals of EU-HIP, as the main objectives of each WP are the necessary steps to reach EU-HIP success (step 1 and 2 of Figure 1).

Importantly, all objectives and indicators were written following a SMART approach – Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound, which is a well-accepted tool for developing effective and measurable objectives and KPIs.³

The third step entailed clearly identifying the WP / task leaders responsible for executing each specific objective. This step was critical to ensure that everyone working in the project is aware of their roles and can be held accountable for the objectives they are responsible for.

The fourth step was aimed at identifying indicators, which are variables that measure the performance of an action and the level to which the objectives are reached. This activity is critical to quantify the achievement of each objective and provides a clear framework for evaluation.

Subsequently, target values were established for each indicator which were defined as measurable targets. This helps to set expectations for the level of performance needed to achieve each objective (step 5 of Figure 1).

The sixth step involved defining the source and method of verification that will allow to validate the achievement of the respective indicator. This step ensures that the data collected is reliable and valid, and that the monitoring process is consistent and effective. The evaluation tools were chosen based on the principle that they should be simple to use, well-known, and simple to integrate into the work processes planned for EU-HIP.

The seventh step consisted in specifying the time intervals at which each indicator will be evaluated. This helps to ensure that the evaluation process is timely and efficient, and that the necessary adjustments can be made in a timely manner.

Finally, the last step focused on ensuring a mechanism in place for the continuous monitoring of the evaluation plan. This is essential to ensure that the plan can be adapted to possible changes at the task / WP / project level, as well as to ensure that it remains relevant and effective throughout the project's lifecycle. All changes to the evaluation plan will be communicated to the relevant parties.

3.2. Evaluation roles and responsibilities

A major part of evaluation activities will be carried out by WP3, which is responsible for data collection, analysis and report. WPs Leaders are required to give input and feedback for data to be collected from WPs, and relevant participants (as applicable) when data cannot be collected by WP3.

In addition, the **Steering Board (SB)** will be involved in the evaluation activities and WP3 will present and discuss the evaluation results and evaluation report at the SB meetings. The **Project Management Team**, which is composed by the coordination team and WP Leaders will be requested to specify, report and provide input for verification of the defined indicators directly linked to the respective WP work plan, using a questionnaire provided by WP3.

³ Bjerke, M. B and Renger, R. Being smart about writing SMART objectives. Evaluation and Program Planning. 2017, Vol 61, 125-127.

3.3. Evaluation methods and tools

The project evaluation will be performed through a “triangulated” approach, meaning that different evaluation instruments, ranging from on-spot surveys in meetings, via observation and document analysis to e-mail surveys with WP-leads and co-leads will be used. The necessary tools to support information collection (e.g., Mentimeter® and JotForm) are available for the work.

The Evaluation framework forms are the key evaluation tool representing a consolidated data collection tool, and the results will be compiled in the different evaluation reports to be shared in consortium’s meetings.

The evaluation matrix was created in close cooperation with all WP leaders, and it will be maintained by WP3. This evaluation matrix helps to better demonstrate the complex correlation of several aspects that are important to reflect on and helps to gather a holistic view of the project’s development.

The platforms chosen to conduct the questionnaires are listed below. It should be noted that adjustments to these tools may be needed throughout the project; however, all parties involved will be informed of such changes.

Surveys

The evaluation surveys will be sent out throughout the project’s life duration at well-defined intervals, with the aim of collecting information and feedback from WP / task leaders. As previously mentioned, the platforms used for the surveys were selected based on the criteria:

- B. simple to use,
- C. well-known, and
- D. simple to integrate into the work processes planned for EU-HIP.

► JotForm surveys

JotForm⁴ is a well-known online platform that allows to build different forms and collect different type of data. This platform will be used to collect information and feedback related to deliverables submission and milestones completion as well as KPIs achievement, giving special attention to any deviations from the project timeline. Annex 1 shows an example of a survey created using this platform to evaluate WPs activities progression and Annexes 2 and 3 summarize de action’s planned milestones and deliverables, respectively.

Whereas the WP and task leaders (Table 2) are requested to submit answers for the questionnaire, WP3 is responsible for data collection and analysis of the submitted answers, as well as its interpretation. The results from the survey are to be included in all evaluation reports.

⁴ <https://www.jotform.com/>

TABLE 2 - WP EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRES

Target group	Mini questionnaire
WP1 Leader and co-leader	Referring to the efficiency of the project management and coordination.
WP2 Leader and co-leader	Referring to the efficiency of the dissemination of the project's outcomes to relevant audiences.
WP4 Leader and co-leader	Referring to facilitators as well as challenges for sustainability of the activities and infrastructures and finding solutions.
WP5 leader and co-leader	Referring to Member States specific tasks and activities in the aim of strengthening national IT systems towards interoperability with HERA's IT platform.

► **Mentimeter**

To measure the effectiveness of the project consortium meetings and the coordination team effectiveness in real-time, an online tool called Mentimeter⁵ will be used. The purpose of these brief surveys is to collect data that reflect the ability of the consortium to provide relevant information on upcoming or past meetings and to evaluate also WP1, WP4 and WP5 activities. The proposed Mentimeter tool allows real-time voting to engage the meeting audience. This tool will be used towards the end of SB meetings, workshops, and other relevant meetings to evaluate the effectiveness of the meeting's agenda, as well as providing information on the consortium's meetings.

The questions asked to the respective meeting participants aim to always follow the same sequence. This allows both the evaluation of specific meetings, as well as evaluation of meeting quality development over time.

3.4. EU-HIP and WP Objectives and Key Performance Indicators

The EU-HIP activities will address a number of specific needs with the ambition that both the Member States and HERA IT systems can operate and exchange data in a coordinated and more automated way. The activities cover aspects related to intelligence gathering and medical countermeasures, both with several specific areas (aspects):

- a. HERA IT platform will gather intelligence on public health threats of many origins (biological, chemical, environmental, unknown), notably natural, accidental or deliberate, and on medical countermeasures.
- b. When looking into relevant specific aspects concerning medical countermeasures, HERA IT platform will gather intelligence on medical countermeasures characteristics, needs, supply chain (shortages, vulnerabilities and strategic dependencies), and preparedness level.

⁵ <https://www.mentimeter.com>

Intelligence on health threats will be gathered from various data and information sources, including existing event-based and indicator-based surveillance systems, with the aim to ensure the appropriate preparedness and response in terms of medical countermeasures. Intelligence will also be gathered on countermeasures of horizontal nature applicable and relevant to more than one specific health threat.

As previously mentioned, the main objectives and KPIs of EU-HIP were mapped against each WP workplan. Based on this work, specific WP objectives and indicators were created that will serve as the main evaluation criteria to monitor the project effectiveness. The indicators are linked to a specific WP, allowing to assess the WP contribution to the overall project achievements.

The specific EU-HIP objectives and KPIs are presented below.

3.4.1. EU-HIP specific objectives

EU-HIP project has identified 2 main needs based on the overall call objectives. For these needs, 6 specific objectives were developed that are expected to be achieved during the project lifetime (Figure 2).

FIGURE 2 – EU-HIP NEEDS AND SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES.

3.4.2. EU-HIP Key Performance Indicators

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are quantifiable values that are used to evaluate how well a project, service, product, process, or activity is accomplishing its goals⁶. KPIs are a crucial tool for tracking progress and any deviations while also proactively assessing and managing the performance of the entire project. As was already indicated, a SMART methodology was used to create KPIs, however due to the current state of the HERA IT system, a flexible methodology was also required.

The progress towards the EU-HIP objectives to be achieved will be tracked and reported based on the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) as indicated in the table below (Table 3).

TABLE 3 - EU-HIP KPIs AND ASSOCIATED SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	Baseline	Target	Related Specific Objectives	Responsible WP
KPI 1 Collection, availability and accessibility of national/regional data categories relevant to HERA's mandate for better preparedness and response to health threats	No data	Key data of at least three relevant categories available and accessible, as defined in dialogue with HERA.	2,3,6	WP4 and WP5
KPI 2 Number of IT modules/systems that exchange data with the HERA IT tool	No data; the HERA's IT platform is being developed	At least 15 IT modules/systems	2,3,5,6	WP5
KPI 3 Number of areas (i.e. aspects of intelligence gathering and of medical countermeasures) covered in the national/regional IT systems that are interoperable with HERA IT platform	No data; the HERA's IT platform is being developed	At least 3 examples of IT systems that cover different areas under intelligence gathering and different areas concerning medical countermeasures.	1,2,3,4,5	WP5
KPI 4 Number of Member States with intelligence gathering IT systems (as defined in dialogue with HERA)	No data	At least 10 Member States.	1,2,3,5,6	WP5

⁶ European Commission, Directorate-General for Informatics, PM², Project management methodology: guide 3.0, Publications Office of the European Union, 2018, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2799/755246>

KPI 5 Exchanging experiences of work that is conducted during the project duration, between countries	Not applicable	At least 5 country visits performed during the EU-HIP action duration	4	WP1, WP4 and WP5
KPI 6 Mechanisms for ensuring coordination between participating countries, HERA and key stakeholders	Structures and processes currently in development	At least 1 mechanism / structure / process adopted by at least 5 consortium participants	5	WP1, WP4 and WP5
KPI 7 Dissemination to support awareness on EU-HIP, contributing to increasing general understanding of importance of IT systems, intelligence gathering and medical countermeasures	Negligible social media attention	#EUHIP hashtag used at least 100 times on social media.	6	WP1, WP2, WP4 and WP5

Note: Important definitions are being discussed with HERA and will be agreed upon in a coordinated manner. The information of this table was extracted from EU-HIP Grant Agreement.

Different Work Packages will be essential to achieve both EU-HIP objectives and KPIs. Deliverable 1.2 – EU-HIP: Key advancements will summarise the main outputs achieved by EU-HIP, including KPI achievement.

KPIs will also be assessed during the project by collecting data from WP leaders through questionnaires.

3.4.3. Work Packages evaluation plan

To assess the extent to which the EU-HIP action reaches the general objectives defined in the projects plan, WP3 – Evaluation will measure at least one indicator for each WP specific objectives that, in combination, will provide evidence of the extent to which the action achieved the general objectives and KPIs.

For each indicator, a brief description is presented to ensure the general understanding of what is being measured. Indicators and target values were defined as specific and measurable terms in order to allow a SMART evaluation of the project. All indicators have a corresponding source of verification that acts as evidence demonstrating that the indicator and its target value were achieved, as well as how this was done.

The time of verification was created based on the planned due date and frequency of the activity. This time of verification was then aligned with the WP3 evaluation timeline, which will be discussed on the next subsection.

The WP evaluation plan was validated by all WP leaders, and it will be monitored throughout the project duration to ensure that the plan can be adapted to possible changes at the task / WP / project level, as well as to ensure that it remains relevant and effective throughout the project's lifecycle. All changes to the evaluation plan will be communicated to the relevant parties.

A template was created for the WP specific evaluation plan, and below an example is provided (Table 4 and Annex 4). The detailed evaluation plan of each WP is documented in an internal excel file⁷, which was validated by the respective WP leaders and coordination. Annexes 5 to 8 summarize the mapping of WP specific objectives with EU-HIP main KPIs and objectives.

TABLE 4 – PARTIAL EXAMPLE OF EVALUATION PLAN OF WP2.

EU-HIP Main Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific Objective 4: Establish collaborative structures and processes to enable collaboration and sharing of experience among countries included in EU-HIP. • Specific Objective 5: Establish collaborative structures and processes with external stakeholders in countries included in EU-HIP, as well as with HERA and relevant EU agencies (e.g., establishment of a board, meetings, etc) • Specific Objective 6: Create structures and platforms to disseminate experiences to support Member States that are not part of EU-HIP. 			
WP specific Objectives	O2.1 EU-HIP Communication & Dissemination Channels			
KPI contribution	Relevant to achieve KPI 5 and 7			
Responsibility	T2.3 leader (CIPH)			
Method for data collection by WP3	Questionnaire/survey to WP / Task leader			
Indicators				
One Website and social media accounts created and delivered	Number of visits / Engagement levels	Number of #EUHIP hashtags used on relevant social media	Number of Project leaflets published	Number of newsletters published
Short description				
Setup of project website as sub-page to SSI webpages, and the creation of 2 social media accounts for EU-HIP	It measures the engagement levels by monitoring the number of visits on the website. Twitter and LinkedIn statistics will also be measured.	It measures the engagement levels by monitoring the number of EU-HIP hashtags used throughout relevant social media, such as Twitter and LinkedIn.	Creation of the project leaflet to establish a design and template for the whole project.	Develop and publish EU-HIP newsletter, highlighting the main outcomes of the project
Target Value				

⁷ [WP3 Evaluation Plan Proposal 23_03_151.xlsx](#) (access restricted by EU-HIP Consortium Members)

M1	10% increase in key statics at M30 compared to M1-3	100 times	1 (M4)	9
Source of Verification				
Link of the website & social media (MS3)	Project Deliverable (D2.1 - Dissemination report)	Project Deliverable (D2.1 - Dissemination report)	MS4 Project leaflet	Newsletter Link
Time of Verification				
M5-6	M5-6; M11-12 M17-18; M22-23; M27-28	M17-18 M22-23 M27-28	M5-6	M5-6; M11-12 M17-18; M22-23; M27-28

WP3 – Evaluation will also assess milestones achievement and deliverables timely submission using a survey for this purpose⁸.

3.5. Evaluation timeline

The project's evaluation timeline offers a methodical way to gauge performance and track progress. The evaluation timeframe was broken down into five key periods, spaced by 6-month periods (Figure 3 and Annex 9), allowing to gather information in a timely and efficient manner, as well as adapt the evaluation plan as needed.

FIGURE 3 – MAIN PERIOD OF EVALUATION.

This timeline was defined in accordance with the evaluation plan and report delivery date. Importantly, the work predicted for the last month (M30) will be assessed in a specific survey for this purpose, so that this information can be integrated in the evaluation report.

⁸ Annexes 2 and 3 summarize the expected due dates for EU-HIP milestones and deliverables. Annex 1 shows an example of a survey that will be used to monitor both the indicators, milestones and deliverables.

The evaluation reporting will be carried out during two main reporting periods as explained below:

Evaluation activities in the 1 st Reporting Period	Evaluation activities in the 2 nd Reporting Period
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Development of the Evaluation Plan (D3.1);• Preparation of evaluation tools and templates;• Data collection and analysis (including survey to WPs leaders) for the evaluation periods M5–6 and M11–12.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Data collection and analysis (including survey to WPL) for the evaluation periods M17–18, M22–23, M27–28, as well as M30.• Development of drafts for the interim (MS6) and final evaluation report (MS7);• Development of the Evaluation Report (D3.2).

4. Conclusion

The evaluation plan is an essential component of any project that helps to ensure that the project is producing the desired results and that the objectives are being reached. This evaluation plan offers a guide for tracking development, recognizing strengths and limitations of EU-HIP. It will serve as an important tool to capture useful data for informed conclusions about the way forward.

Importantly, due to the interdependency with HERA's IT platform development work, EU-HIP evaluation plan will be continuously monitored and updated, as needed, in order to ensure its applicability and relevance. This work will be coordinated with the coordination team and WP leaders.

Overall, the evaluation plan provides a clear framework for assessing the progress of the project and acts as crucial instrument to enhance efficiency and contribute to the sustainability of the EU-HIP.

Annexes

Annex 1 – Example of a survey form created using JotForm

Please fill in WP2 target values *

	Target Value	Observed Value	Explain any deviations from target value, if applicable	Please provide a source of verification if applicable. Otherwise specify
1-. [O2.1] <u>One website and social media accounts created and delivered.</u>	▼			
2-. [O2.1] <u>Number of visits / engagement levels</u>	▼			
3-. [O2.1] Number of #EUHIP hashtags used on relevant social media	▼			
4-. [O2.1] Number of Project leaflets published	▼			
5-. [O2.1] Number of newsletters published	▼			
6-. [O2.2] Number of key stakeholders and target groups analysed	▼			
7-. [O2.2] Elaboration of one Layman Dissemination Report	▼			
8-. [O2.2] Elaboration of one report on dissemination activities	▼			

FIGURE 4 – EXAMPLE OF SECTION I– INDICATORS THAT WILL BE USED TO MEASURE THE SPECIFIED TARGET VALUES, SOURCE OF VERIFICATION AND TRACK DEVIATIONS. AN INSTRUCTION TEXT WILL BE DISPLAYED AT BEGINNING OF EACH SECTION TO SUPPORT USERS IN COMPLETING THE TABLE (PLEASE SEE FIGURE 8 AS AN EXAMPLE).

Please justify any target values deviations and/or provide additional comments, if applicable

Voltar
Próximo

FIGURE 5 – EXAMPLE OF A FIELD FOR WP LEADERS TO PROVIDE JUSTIFICATIONS ON POSSIBLE DEVIATIONS AND ADDITIONAL COMMENTS.

Please fill in the information regarding WP2 deliverables *

	Submitted on time on the EC Portal	Submitted with delay on the EC Portal	Not submitted on the EC Portal	Please provide a source of verification if applicable. Otherwise specify
D2.1 (M30)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
D2.2 (M30)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	

Deviations to Report?

Please Select
▼

FIGURE 6 – EXAMPLE OF SECTION II– DELIVERABLES THAT WILL BE USED TO MONITOR THE TIMELY SUBMISSION OF DELIVERABLES.

Please justify why, if any, WP2 Deliverable was submitted with delay, if applicable.

Please justify why, if any, WP2 Deliverable was not submitted, if applicable.

FIGURE 7 – EXAMPLE OF A FIELD TO OBTAIN DATA REGARDING ANY DELAYS AND ALTERATIONS REGARDING DELVIERABLE SUBMISSION.

Section III - Milestones

Instructions:

- In the table: Select the applicable status of achievement for each milestone. Please indicate the source of verification that will be used to verify the selected option.
- In the text box: If applicable, please add an explanation about any deviations from the expected status of achievement.

WP2 Milestones:

- **MS3** - Website and Social Media
- **MS4** - Project Leaflet

Please fill in the information regarding WP2 milestones *

	Achieved	Achieved with delay	Not achieved	Please provide a source of verification if applicable. Otherwise specify
MS3 (M1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
MS4 (M4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	

FIGURE 8 – EXAMPLE OF SECTION III – MILESTONES THAT WILL BE USED TO MONITOR THE ACHIEVEMENT OF MILESTONES.

Annex 2 – List of EU-HIP milestones (MSs) and respective deadlines

Due Date	# MS	Deliverable Name	WP
M1 (Jan.23)	MS3	Website and social media	WP2
M2 (Feb.23)	MS5	Objective evaluation criteria defined	WP3
M4 (Apr.23)	MS4	Project leaflet	WP2
	MS9	State of play of AI usage for public health surveillance	WP4
M5 (May.23)	MS8	Data collection methodology and interim landscape mapping reports	WP4
M6 (Jun.23)	MS1	First version of DMP	WP1
M9 (Sep.23)	MS8	Data collection methodology and interim landscape mapping reports	WP4
M10 (Oct.23)	MS8	Data collection methodology and interim landscape mapping reports	WP4
	MS13	MS Workshop series on “state-of-play” to achieve a common framework	WP5
M12 (Dec.23)	MS14	MS “state-of-play” analysis and comparison	WP5
	MS15	An initial outline of initiatives underway within MS	WP5
M12-M24 (Dec.23 – Dec.24)	MS11	Workshops & country visits	WP4
M12-M24 (Dec.23 – Dec.24)	MS11	Workshops & country visits	WP4
M14 (Feb.24)	MS6	Draft of interim evaluation report	WP3
	MS10	EU-MS best practice	WP5
M16 (Apr.24)	MS12	Initial co-designed recommendations and sustainability proposal	WP4
M21 (Sep.24)	MS2	First draft of D1.2 (EU-HIP: Key advancements)	WP1
M24 (Dec.24)	MS16	An agreed set of interoperability standards with the HERA IT platform	WP5
M28 (Apr.25)	MS7	Draft of final evaluation report	WP3

Annex 3 – List of EU-HIP deliverables (Ds) and respective deadlines

Due Date	# D	Deliverable Name	WP
M3 (Mar.23)	D3.1	Evaluation Plan	WP3
M6 (Jun.23)	D1.1	Data Management Plan	WP1
M11 (Nov.23)	D4.1	Landscape analysis final report	WP4
M18 (Jun.24)	D5.1	Needs analysis report	WP5
M24 (Dec.24)	D4.2	AI usage for public health surveillance in EU	WP4
	D4.4	Reports on the co-design meetings	WP4
M30 (Jun.25)	D1.2	EU-HIP: Key advancements	WP1
	D2.1	Layman Dissemination Report	WP2
	D2.2	Dissemination report	WP2
	D3.2	Evaluation report	WP3
	D4.3	HERA Ecosystem Sustainability: Recommendations for maintenance and scaling up from EU-HIP consortium	WP4
	D5.2	National roadmaps to implementations	WP5
	D5.3	National IT systems meeting interoperability standards	WP5

Annex 4 – Work Package 2 specific evaluation plan

#	Indicator	Short description	Target Value	Source of verification	Time of verification	EU-HIP General dependencies
WP Specific Objective – O2.1 EU-HIP Communication & Dissemination Channels						
15.1	One Website and social media accounts created and delivered	Setup of project website as sub-page to SSI webpages, and the creation of 2 social media accounts for EU-HIP	M1	Link of the website & social media (MS3)	M5-6	All WPs
15.2	Number of visits / Engagement levels	It measures the engagement levels by monitoring the number of visits on the website. Twitter and LinkedIn statistics will also be measured	10% increase in key statics at M30 compared to M1-3	Project Deliverable (D2.1 - Dissemination report)	M5-6, M11-12, M17-18, M22-23, M27-28	All WPs
15.3	Number of #EUHIP hashtags used on relevant social media	It measures the engagement levels by monitoring the number of EU-HIP hashtags used throughout relevant social media, such as Twitter and LinkedIn.	100 times	Project Deliverable (D2.1 - Dissemination report)	M17-18, M22-23, M27-28	All WPs
15.4	Number of Project leaflets published	Creation of the project leaflet to establish a design and template for the whole project.	1 (M4)	MS4 Project leaflet	M5-6	All WPs
15.5	Number of newsletters published	Develop and publish EU-HIP newsletter, highlighting the main outcomes of the project	9	Newsletter link	M5-6, M11-12, M17-18, M22-23, M27-28	All WPs
WP Specific Objective – O2.2 Communication and dissemination general activities						
15.6	Number of key stakeholders &	It measures the number of stakeholders and target groups analysed to identify all	3	Project Deliverable (D2.1 -	M11-12	WP1, WP5

#	Indicator	Short description	Target Value	Source of verification	Time of verification	EU-HIP General dependencies
	target groups analysed	categories of the population that could directly benefit from the project, who could be the best advocates and those who could develop resistance to the implementation of the project. This indicator contributes to mapping of existing projects and initiatives with overlapping or similar activities, by WP1 and WP5.		Dissemination report)		
15.7	Elaboration of one Layman Dissemination Report	It measures the disseminate the EU-HIP project and its results for the general public	1 (M30)	Project Deliverable (D2.1 - Dissemination report)	M27-28 M30	All WPs
15.8	Elaboration of one report on dissemination activities	It measures the disseminate the EU-HIP project and its results, events and all-around activities that were done throughout the lifetime of the project, ensuring continuity and a future for the project. It measures the outreach of the project.	1 (M30)	Project Deliverable (D2.2 - Dissemination report)	M27-28 M30	ALL WPs

Annex 5 – Mapping of objectives and KPIs of EU-HIP and Work Package 1

WP Specific Objective	Contribution to EU-HIP Main Objective	Contribution to EU-HIP KPIs	Responsibility
O1.1 Project Coordination and Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not applicable 	Not applicable	Coordination Team (T1.1 Lead, SSI)
O1.2 Timely and robust financial management and payments to beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not applicable 	Not applicable	Coordination/Financial Team (T1.1 Lead, SSI)
O1.3 Collaboration with stakeholders O1.4 Data Management Plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specific Objective 4: Establish collaborative structures and processes to enable collaboration and sharing of experience among countries included in EU-HIP (e.g., country visits, co-design workshops). Specific Objective 5: Establish collaborative structures and processes with external stakeholders in countries included in EU-HIP, as well as with HERA and relevant EU agencies Specific Objective 6: Create structures and platforms to disseminate experiences to support Member States that are not part of EU-HIP" 	Relevant to achieve: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI5 KPI6 	Coordination Team (T1.2 and T1.4 Lead, SSI) Coordination Team (T1.3 Lead, SSI)
O1.5 EU-HIP Key Advancements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specific Objective 2: Strengthen national IT systems addressing country-specific needs 	Relevant to achieve: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI7 	Coordination Team (T1.1 Lead, SSI)

Annex 6 – Mapping of objectives and KPIs of EU-HIP and Work Package 2

WP Specific Objective	Contribution to EU-HIP Main Objective	Contribution to EU-HIP KPIs	Responsibility
O2.1 EU-HIP Communication & Dissemination Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specific Objective 4: Establish collaborative structures and processes to enable collaboration and sharing of experience among countries included in EU-HIP 		T2.3 Leader (CIPH)
O2.2 Communication and Dissemination General Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specific Objective 5: Establish collaborative structures and processes with external stakeholders in countries included in EU-HIP, as well as with HERA and relevant EU agencies (e.g., establishment of a board, meetings, etc.) Specific Objective 6: Create structures and platforms to disseminate experiences to support Member States that are not part of EU-HIP (e.g., newsletter, workshops, webinars) 	Relevant to achieve: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI5 KPI7 	T2.2 Leader (CIPH) T2.4 Leader (CIPH) T2.5 Leader (CIPH)

Annex 6 – Mapping of objectives and KPIs of EU-HIP and Work Package 4

WP Specific Objective	Contribution to EU-HIP Main Objective	Contribution to EU-HIP KPIs	Responsibility
O4.1 Landscape analysis – Digital ecosystem for health crisis preparedness and response	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specific Objective 1: Obtain an overview of current key aspects of national IT systems and assess the compatibility with HERA's IT platform 	Relevant to achieve: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI-1 	T4.1 Leader (THL)
O4.2 Landscape on AI usage for public health surveillance in EU and EU-MS Best practices		Relevant as a baseline for KPI-3	T4.2 Leader (SPMS)
O4.3 Collaborative structures and processes with EU-HIP consortium participants to discuss sustainability aspects of EU-HIP.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specific Objective 4: Establish collaborative structures and processes to enable collaboration and sharing of experience among countries included in EU-HIP (e.g., country visits, co-design workshops). 	Relevant to achieve <ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI-5 KPI-6 KPI-7 	T4.3 Leader (MIN-SAL, THL)
O4.4 Collaborative structures and processes with key stakeholders during the project, especially MS not participating in EU-HIP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specific Objective 5: Establish collaborative structures and processes with external stakeholders in countries included in EU-HIP, as well as with HERA and relevant EU agencies (e.g., establishment of a board, meetings, etc) 	Relevant to achieve: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI-5 KPI-6 KPI-7 	T4.4 Leader (MIN-SAL, THL)
O4.5 HERA Ecosystem Sustainability: Recommendations for maintenance and scaling up from EU-HIP consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specific Objective 6: Create structures and platforms to disseminate experiences to support Member States that are not part of EU-HIP (e.g., newsletter, workshops, webinars) 	Relevant to achieve: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI-5 KPI-6 KPI-7 	T4.3 Leader (MIN-SAL, THL)
O4.6 Recommendations on AI usage for public health surveillance in EU		Relevant to achieve: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI-5 KPI-6 KPI-7 	T4.3 Leader (MIN-SAL, THL)

Annex 8 – Mapping of objectives and KPIs of EU-HIP and Work Package 5

WP Specific Objective	EU-HIP Main Objective contribution	EU-HIP KPI	Responsibility
O5.1 Specific technical needs analyses of MS IT-systems and infrastructures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific Objective 1: Obtain an overview of current key aspects of national IT systems and assess the compatibility with HERA's IT platform • Specific Objective 4: Establish collaborative structures and processes to enable collaboration and sharing of experience among countries included in EU-HIP • Specific Objective 6: Create structures and platforms to disseminate experiences to support Member States that are not part of EU-HIP 	Relevant to achieve: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI1 • KPI4 • KPI5 • KPI6 	Task 5.1 leader – Sciensano
O5.2 Improvement of digital epidemiological surveillance infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific Objective 2: Strengthen national IT system addressing country-specific needs • Specific Objective 5: Establish collaborative structures and processes with external stakeholders in countries included in EU-HIP, as well as with HERA and relevant EU agencies 	Relevant to achieve: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI1 • KPI4 • KPI7 	Task 5.2 leader – NPIH-NO
O5.3 Interoperability with the HERA IT platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific Objective 3: Improve interoperability of key aspects of national IT systems with HERA' IT platform • Specific Objective 5: Establish collaborative structures and processes with external stakeholders in countries included in EU-HIP, as well as with HERA and relevant EU agencies • Specific Objective 6: Create structures and platforms to disseminate experiences to support Member States that are not part of EU-HIP" 	Relevant to achieve: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI2 • KPI3 • KPI6 	Task 5.3 leader – Sciensano

Annex 9 – WP3 activities timeline

